

Parametric study of a dual-band quasi-Yagi antenna for LTE application

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ABSTRACT

Due to small size and lightweight properties, the development of microstrip (MS) patch antennas for wireless communication has become one of the mobile application devices in demand in recent years. This has helped to reduce reliance on wired cables. In this paper, a study has been performed on MS antenna by developing a quasi-Yagi structure on a fire retardant-4 (FR-4) substrate with a MS to coplanar strip line (CPS) transition feeding technique. The antenna is designed by using computer simulation technology (CST) to achieve the desired resonant frequency and bandwidth. The proposed dual band quasi-Yagi antenna has impedance bandwidths of approximately 0.3 GHz and 0.22 GHz resonating at 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz, respectively, which makes it suitable for long-term evolution (LTE) applications. Eight-director elements in four pairs are constructed to achieve directivity with magnitudes of 6 dB and 8.3 dBi at both resonant frequencies, 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz, respectively. Different parametric studies have also been performed to characterize the antenna radiation characteristics. The return loss, voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR), front to back (F/B) ratio and far-field radiation are analyzed and discussed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Microstrip (MS) patch antenna is widely utilized in wireless applications because of its compact size, lightweight, and inexpensive construction cost [1]-[5]. This reduces the dependencies on the wired cables hence occupies less space. The number of people using smartphones, computers, smart TVs, and many other internet-connected wireless devices is rising rapidly. The need for creating high-speed wireless networks has increased in response to this enormous number of wireless devices [6]. Today's cellular technology is developing quickly, and we rely on it to withstand our heavy use. Most mobile users and the IoT are adopting the newest technologies in this area because of the necessity for rapid data transfer [7], [8]. MS patch antennas can be designed with different design structures such as rectangular, circular, triangular,

Fire retardant-4 (FR-4) is the antenna substrate material, and its dielectric constant is 4.3 and its thickness is 1.56 mm. In the configuration, the MS dipole is employed to produce a TE₀ mode with the electric vector (E) perpendicular to the propagation axis. Transmission line model can be used to design the driven element. The following describe the calculation of λ , L_{dr} and W_{dr} :

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{12d}{W_{dr}}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where, ϵ_r =dielectric constant, d =substrate thickness, and W_{dr} =width of the driven element. The length of the driven element (L_{dr}) is half the wavelength which can be calculated using (2):

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f \sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}} \quad (2)$$

Where λ =wavelength in meter, c =speed of light, and f =frequency.

Conventional feeding techniques using MS lines have an unbalanced characteristic that can affect the radiation of a printed dipole element. Thus, a CPS transition is used to avoid unwanted radiation. Because the CPS line only accepts even mode, a balun phase shifter is used to balance the CPS feeding by generating a 180° phase difference between MS and CPS at both resonant frequencies of 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz [24]. This can be achieved by adjusting the length of the delay line on one of the branches such that:

$$\frac{\lambda_g}{4} = L_3 - L_2 \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_g = \frac{c}{f} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{c}{2a \times f}\right)^2}} \quad (4)$$

Where, a =width of MS line.

A quarter-wave transformer line with characteristic impedance of Z_0 is utilized to match the 50 Ω port impedance to the 25 Ω T-junction [25]. Using the following equation, the Z_0 with length of $\lambda_g/4$ is 35.35 Ω .

$$Z_0 = \sqrt{Z_{in} Z_L} \quad (5)$$

Where, Z_{in} =input impedance, Z_L =load impedance.

To ensure the antenna is optimized for the required LTE frequency band, it is necessary to do study on the antenna's design parameters including effect of number of director element, effect of tuning ground plane (reflector) length, effect on tuning length of driven element and effect of dielectric thickness. The antenna is 180.13 mm in length and 99.59 mm in width. CST software is used to increase the length of the driven element from its original value of 58.25 mm (based on the formula presented in (1) to (5)) to 71.20 mm. The ground plane with length and width of 43.50 mm and 99.59 mm, respectively, acts as a reflector element to enhance the radiation beam at the plane of the driven element. Four paired i.e. eight director elements are vertically spaced by S1, S2, and S3 respectively and horizontally spaced by G1, G2, G3, and G4 respectively. These spacing are optimized and determined to provide higher gain of the antenna in the LTE operating frequency range. The geometrical parameters for the proposed quasi-Yagi antenna design are listed in Table 1. Figure 3(a) and 3(b) show the front view and back view of the fabricated quasi-Yagi antenna.

Table 1. Geometrical parameters of the quasi-Yagi antenna

Name	Value	Name	Value	Name	Value	Name	Value	Name	Value
W_{dr}	5.50 mm	L_{dir1}	36.07 mm	t	1.56 mm	L_1	29.03 mm	S_3	4.29 mm
L_{dr}	71.20 mm	L_{dir2}	56.99 mm	h	0.02 mm	L_2	21.75 mm	G_1	0.50 mm
W_{dir1}	15.38 mm	L_{dir3}	57.52 mm	W_s	99.59 mm	L_3	43.50 mm	G_2	7.47 mm
W_{dir2}	15.38 mm	L_{dir4}	56.48 mm	L_s	180.13 mm	S_1	3.51 mm	G_3	18.88 mm
W_{dir3}	15.38 mm	W_2	5.90 mm	L_g	48.90 mm	S_2	4.18 mm	G_4	40.34 mm
W_{dir4}	15.38 mm	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 3. Fabricated prototype of the quasi-Yagi antenna (a) front view and (b) back view

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amount of power reflected by a transmission line is measured by its return loss (S11). When the magnitude of S11 is lower than -10 dB then the antenna reflects as little energy as possible. The optimized quasi-Yagi antenna has two resonance frequencies of 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz, and a graph of the simulated return loss within the range of 1.6 GHz to 3 GHz is shown in Figure 4. First resonant at 1.80 GHz has a return loss of -65.23 dB, and the other at 2.60 GHz has -31.55 dB. Voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) measures voltage variances along the transmission line. The standard set for an antenna requires a VSWR to be less than 2 for the least variances equivalent to minimum -10 dB level of S11 which is depicted in Figure 5. The gain and directional nature of the quasi-Yagi antenna in both operating bands are depicted in Figure 6. The antenna has a peak gain of 6 dB and a directivity of 8.3 dBi.

Figure 4. S11 parameter of the quasi-Yagi antenna

Figure 5. VSWR of the quasi-Yagi antenna

Figure 6. Gain and directivity of the quasi-Yagi antenna

Figure 7(a) and 7(b) depict magnetic and electric fields at an angle of theta equal to 90° and an angle of ϕ equal to 0° and 90° . At the 1.80 resonant frequency, both the E-field and H-prominent field's lobes are centered at 4° , 83° , 83° for $\phi=0^{\circ}$, 90° and $\theta=90^{\circ}$. The magnitudes of E-fields are -39.9 dBV/m, -31.8 dBV/m, -31.7 dBV/m at $\phi=0^{\circ}$, 90° and $\theta=90^{\circ}$. The -3 dB angular beamwidth, or half power beamwidth is located at 83.6° , 123.2° , 74.8° and the side lobe level is -13.7 dB, -15.2 dB, -14.1 dB at $\phi=0^{\circ}$, 90° and $\theta=90^{\circ}$. According to the arrangement of the omnidirectional radiation patterns, the Yagi antenna emits radiation in all directions that are perpendicular to the x-axis. Analysis shows that this omnidirectional Yagi antenna is a good option for LTE networks.

Figure 7. Radiation patterns of the quasi-Yagi antenna at (a) 1.80 GHz and (b) 2.60 GHz

4. PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS

The effectiveness of a MS type Yagi-Uda antenna depends on several factors, including the substrate's thickness, the lengths of the feed and parasitic components, and the spacing between them. To get the best possible results from an antenna, it is important to determine its geometrical factors through an exhaustive parametric analysis. In this research work, we have conducted an exhaustive parametric study to investigate how the geometrical factors impact the antenna's outgoing signal.

4.1. Effect of changing the number of director elements

There are two scenarios that are being investigated in this study. The first scenario evaluates the radiation characteristic of the antenna for a different number of director elements (in pairs) along symmetrical lines at G1, G2, G3, and G4. The result of the variation can be depicted in Figure 8. As the

number of director elements increases, the first resonant point is shifted significantly. The reflection coefficients for first resonant frequency are -19 dB, -24 dB, -54 dB, -45 dB, and -67 dB for 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 number directors, respectively. At higher frequency, the second resonant frequency of 2.60 GHz does not show any significant frequency shift with the number of elements, but the magnitude varies such as -20 dB, -40 dB, -26 dB, -30 dB, and -35 dB for 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 number directors. The magnitude variation for both frequencies are influenced by the antenna impedance which can be further studied in a smith chart plot. In this case the eight director element antenna has an impedance of 50Ω at the resonant frequencies.

Figure 8. Effect of changing the number of directors on S11

4.2. Effect of tuning ground plane (reflector) length, L_g

With this adjustment, the ground plane length goes up from 48.9-56.9 mm, an increment of 2 mm in each step. Figure 9 demonstrates the return loss (S11) where the magnitude of S11 reduces and shifts to the left for the first resonant frequency while increasing the length of the ground plane (L_g). For the higher resonant frequency, the return loss also slightly varies, and the resonant frequency significantly shifts to the left of 2.6 GHz. Front to back (F/B) ratio and directivity are also investigated for both frequencies. Table 2 summarizes the results obtained from the study. It shows that, at 1.80 GHz, initially the F/B ratio increases from 13.47-13.61 dB then decreases to 12.76 dB while increasing the length of the L_g from 48.90 mm to 56.90 mm. In the same fashion, at 1.80 GHz, the directivity also increases from 6.63 dBi to 6.74 dBi then decreases to 6.5 dBi. For resonant frequency of 2.60 GHz, initially the F/B increases and later decreases whereas the directivity decreases with increasing the length of L_g . The decrease in F/B is due to increasing back lobe of the radiation since the partial ground plane act as the reflector element.

Figure 9. Effect of tuning ground plane length (L_g) on S11

Table 2. Front-to-back (F/B) ratio and directivity with varying the length of L_g

Resonant frequency L_g (mm)	1.80 GHz		2.60 GHz	
	F/B (dB)	Directivity (dBi)	F/B (dB)	Directivity (dBi)
48.90	13.47	6.63	14.96	8.30
50.90	13.51	6.69	15.39	8.01
52.90	13.61	6.74	15.25	7.96
54.90	13.40	6.71	14.46	7.80
56.90	12.76	6.50	13.09	7.31

4.3. Effect of tuning length of driven element (L_{dr})

The length of the driving element is varied from 63.20-71.20 mm in this study. Figure 10 demonstrates that the first resonant frequency significantly changes with the change of driven element length (L_{dr}) whereas the second resonant frequency remains almost fixed at 2.60 GHz. The quasi-Yagi antenna resonates at 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz with most suitable bandwidths and reflection coefficients for desired LTE spectrum. The reflection coefficients are -67 dB and -35 dB at 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz, respectively, for 71.20 mm length of driven element.

4.4. Effect of substrate thickness (t)

Return loss for various substrate thicknesses (t) is depicted in Figure 11. The thickness of the FR-4 substrate is varied from 1.56-1.76 mm. As the substrate's thickness grows, the quasi-Yagi antenna's resonant frequencies and bandwidths shift significantly. For the thickness of 1.56 mm, the designed quasi-Yagi antenna resonates at the intended frequencies of 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz with good reflection coefficients.

Figure 10. Effect of tuning driven element length (L_{dr}) on S11

Figure 11. Effect of changing substrate thickness (t) on S11

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented a dual-band quasi-Yagi antenna with eight directors. The proposed quasi-Yagi antenna features a dual resonant frequency of 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz respectively. In order to characterize the designed antenna, different parametric studies including effect of number of directors, length of reflector (L_g), driven element (L_{dr}) and thickness of substrate (t) have been conducted. CST software is used to design and examine the aforementioned studies of different parameters. The prototype of the designed quasi-Yagi antenna has been developed in the laboratory. The quasi-Yagi antenna shows good reflection coefficient, gain, directivity, (F/B) ratio and VSWR for the both operating bands of 1.80 GHz and 2.60 GHz. The proposed design may be suitable for the LTE band of mobile communications.

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